

Probabilistic approach to evaluate buckling design allowables for a tailored aircraft composite wing using Quad and Double-Double (DD) laminates

Dr Leonardo Ferreira - FEMTO-ST, Université Marie & Louis Pasteur, France

Mr Filipe Oliveira - UFMG Federal University of Minas Gerais, Brazil

Ms Rosana Silva - UFMG Federal University of Minas Gerais, Brazil

Prof Lucas Vignoli - UFRJ Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil

Prof Carlos Cimini - UFMG Federal University of Minas Gerais, Brazil

OUTLINE

- Motivation
- Problem Statement
- Framework
- Methodology
- Results
- Conclusions

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MOTIVATION

Composites World
December 12, 2014

“Composites in general are **poorly understood**” ...
... “therefore are **not employed optimally**”

John Byrne, VP aircraft materials and structures at Boeing Commercial Airplanes, speaking at CompositesWorld's Carbon Fiber 2014 conference, Dec. 10, 2014

The Wall Street Journal
April 2, 2015

Boeing's Ray Conner said the company isn't likely to repeat the business model that created the Dreamliner. PHOTO: GETTY IMAGES

“It's not to say you don't innovate,” said Mr. Conner. He wants engineers “innovating more on how to [design jets] **more simplistically**, as **opposed to driving more complexity**,” he said. “How do you innovate to make it **more producible**? How do you innovate to make it **more reliable**?”

Our goal: To advocate DD as the best way forward

MOTIVATION

Development Trends in Different Industries

Source: DARPA

MOTIVATION

QUAD:

- 4 angles (0,±45,90)
- Symmetric
- Balanced
- 10% rule
- Heterogeneous

$[0/+45/-45/90]_s$
Class
QUAD legacy

DD:

- 2 angles (Φ, Ψ)
- Non-symmetric
- Non-balanced
- Block repetition
- Homogeneous

$[\pm\Phi/\pm\Psi]_n$
Class
Double-Double

MOTIVATION

Designers in composites:

- Natural “inertia” to accept new design approaches
- Natural unease of breaking established design rules
- More comfortable if could crosscheck old and new designs

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PROBLEM STATEMENT

Given a composite traditional wing (QUAD)

Optimized for elastic buckling analysis (eigenvalue)

Obtain equivalent DD design

Compare A-Basis and B-Basis allowables

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FRAMEWORK

For QUAD and DD:

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METHODOLOGY

Tsai and Pagano (1968) and Tsai and Hahn (1980) demonstrated that $[A^*]$, $[B^*]$ and $[D^*]$ can be expressed as linear functions of the invariants (U_1, U_2, U_3, U_4, U_5) and the so-called **lamination parameters** (in red)

$$U_1^Q = \frac{1}{8}(3Q_{11} + 3Q_{22} + 2Q_{12} + 4Q_{66})$$

$$U_2^Q = \frac{1}{2}(Q_{11} - Q_{22})$$

$$U_3^Q = \frac{1}{8}(Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} - 4Q_{66})$$

$$U_4^Q = \frac{1}{8}(Q_{11} + Q_{22} + 6Q_{12} - 4Q_{66})$$

$$U_5^Q = \frac{1}{8}(Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} + 4Q_{66})$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_{11}^* \\ A_{22}^* \\ A_{12}^* \\ A_{66}^* \\ A_{16}^* \\ A_{26}^* \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & V_1^* & V_2^* & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & -V_1^* & V_2^* & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -V_2^* & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -V_2^* & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & V_3^*/2 & V_4^* & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & V_3^*/2 & -V_4^* & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U_1 \\ U_2 \\ U_3 \\ U_4 \\ U_5 \end{bmatrix}$$

In-Plane Lamination Parameters

$$\begin{bmatrix} D_{11}^* \\ D_{22}^* \\ D_{12}^* \\ D_{66}^* \\ D_{16}^* \\ D_{26}^* \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & W_1^* & W_2^* & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & -W_1^* & W_2^* & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -W_2^* & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -W_2^* & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & W_3^*/2 & W_4^* & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & W_3^*/2 & -W_4^* & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U_1 \\ U_2 \\ U_3 \\ U_4 \\ U_5 \end{bmatrix}$$

Bending Lamination Parameters

~~$$\begin{bmatrix} B_{11}^* \\ B_{22}^* \\ B_{12}^* \\ B_{66}^* \\ B_{16}^* \\ B_{26}^* \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & Y_1^* & Y_2^* & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -Y_1^* & Y_2^* & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -Y_2^* & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -Y_2^* & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & Y_3^*/2 & Y_4^* & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & Y_3^*/2 & -Y_4^* & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} U_1 \\ U_2 \\ U_3 \\ U_4 \\ U_5 \end{bmatrix}$$

Coupling Lamination Parameters~~

Homogenized laminate, i.e.:

$$B_{ij}^* = 0 \quad i=1,2,6 \quad j=1,2,6$$

$$A_{ij}^* = D_{ij}^* \quad i=1,2,6 \quad j=1,2,6$$

$$\begin{aligned} W_1^* &= V_1^* \\ W_2^* &= V_2^* \\ W_3^* &= V_3^* \\ W_4^* &= V_4^* \end{aligned}$$

$$V_1^* = (A_{11}^* - A_{22}^*) / 2U_2$$

$$V_2^* = (A_{11}^* + A_{22}^* - 2U_1) / 2U_3$$

METHODOLOGY

QUAD-DD equivalency in $V_1^*-V_2^*$ space:

DD feasible continuous domain (in red)

QUADs are discrete points

METHODOLOGY

Material (CFRP):
AS4-8552 (Hexcel)
UD Prepreg

$$E_1 = 119 \text{ GPa}$$

$$E_2 = 9.8 \text{ GPa}$$

$$G_{12} = 4.7 \text{ GPa}$$

$$n_{12} = 0.316$$

$$t_k = 0.186 \text{ mm}$$

Six parameters may influence the critical buckling load (P_{cr}):

- E_1 – longitudinal modulus (GPa)
- E_2 – transverse modulus (GPa)
- G_{12} – in-plane shear modulus (GPa)
- n_{12} – major Poisson's ratio
- t_k – ply thickness
- 0° plies angle deviation

METHODOLOGY

Finite Element model

Composite optimized wing (Benchmark wing)

Critical loading case:

$$n_z = 2.5$$

Mach 0.82

MTOW

10,000 m altitude

Hundreds of
different layups

Boundary conditions:
Clamped at root

METHODOLOGY

Monte Carlo Simulation (Parameter Variation)

Parameter	Mean (μ)	Standard Deviation (σ)	4 Standard Deviations (4σ)	Lower Bound ($\mu - 4\sigma$)	Upper Bound ($\mu + 4\sigma$)
E_1	119 GPa	6.00 GPa	24.0 GPa	95.0 GPa	143 GPa
E_2	9.8 GPa	0.3 GPa	1.2 GPa	8.6 GPa	11 GPa
ν_{12}	0.316	0.038	0.153	0.163	0.469
G_{12}	4.7 GPa	0.15 GPa	0.60 GPa	4.1 GPa	5.3 GPa
α	–	–	–	$\alpha - 2^\circ$	$\alpha + 2^\circ$
t	0.186 mm	0.007 mm	0.028 mm	0.158 mm	0.214 mm

Uncertainties – Sobol sensitivity analysis

**Hexcel 8552 AS4 Unidirectional
Prepreg at 190 gsm & 35% RC
Qualification Material Property Data Report**

FAA Special Project Number SP4614WI-Q
NCAMP Test Report Number: CAM-RP-2010-002 Rev A

METHODOLOGY

Surrogate model – Interpolator based in ANN (Artificial Neural Network):

- Training Group: checking the surrogate model
- Validation Group: to make sure the learning is correct
- Test Group: verify the final model independently

Monte Carlo simulations = 1,000 $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Training Group} = 800 \\ \text{Validation Group} = 100 \\ \text{Test Group} = 100 \end{array} \right.$

A-Basis and B-Basis design allowables obtained running the surrogate model for 1,000 samples.

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RESULTS

Deterministic analyses

QUAD

DD equivalent

First 10
buckling
modes

First
buckling
mode

Eigenvalue: 0.77457

Eigenvalue: 0.704776 (-9.0%)

RESULTS

Sensitivity analyses (Sobol indices)

Convergence

Sobol Indices

RESULTS

ANN training

Training Group

Validation Group

Test Group

QUAD

DD equivalent

RESULTS

A-basis and B-basis design allowables

QUAD

DD equivalent

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CONCLUSIONS

- Equivalent DD wing obtained from QUAD wing
- Deterministic analysis showed eigenvalue 9% lower for DD wing
- Probabilistic A- and B-basis eigenvalues around 7% lower for DD
- Equivalence based on A^* matrix (V_1^* - V_2^*)
- D^* matrix may have influence on the DD equivalency (W_1^* - W_2^*)
- Design allowables reasonably equivalent
- Exercise for designers to built confidence in DD
- **Design should be performed originally in DD**

Thank you